

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

2023 ESIL Innovation Summit Evaluation Report

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Introduction

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIIL, www.esiil.org) serves as a data science center of excellence and synthesis center that facilitates collaboration across large, diverse teams through the ESIIL Network. ESIIL brings together a diverse community of environmental and biological data scientists to turn environmental and biological data into actionable understanding and knowledge toward a more sustainable society. The center activities support ESIIL's mission: *“Empower an inclusive and diverse community to accelerate continental-scale environmental data science (EDS)”*.

Toward these efforts, ESIIL held the first annual **ESIIL Environmental Data Science Innovation Summit** on May 23rd – 25th, 2023 in Boulder, CO bringing together Earth and Environmental Data Scientists to build and strengthen the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. The Summit welcomed 202 total attendees, 87% joined the meeting in-person and 13% attended the Summit virtually. The Summit followed an “unconference” meeting format (Budd et al., 2015) that included attendees in the planning of topics and activities in a series of brainstorming sessions that took place prior to the Summit and encouraged participant engagement and involvement in shaping the Summit and feedback each day to inform what was included in subsequent days of the meeting. The overarching goals of the ESIIL Summit were:

- Define a decadal research agenda for the growing field of environmental data science by articulating the most pressing environmental challenges and opportunities for solutions-oriented science, and by bridging environmental and biological sciences, social sciences, and data and computational sciences.
- Build a diverse and inclusive ESIIL Network by establishing collaborations with others from different disciplines, sectors, career stages, and backgrounds around research themes of interest.

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation team used a collaborative approach (King and Stevahn 2013, Shulha et al. 2016) to design [the Summit evaluation activities, meeting with the project leadership to discuss survey development prior to the event. An online, pre-Summit survey was sent to all registered Summit attendees the week before the Summit began. Attendees were reminded about the survey on the first day and provided with a QR code to scan at their tables (or a link for virtual participants). On the final day of the Summit, attendees were invited to take an online reflection survey to share their experiences of the Pre-Summit and Summit Events. To reduce the number of surveys participants were given, questions for a general Needs Assessment and Social Network Analysis for the Environmental Data Science community were included in the pre-Summit survey. These responses are shared in separate reports.

ESIIL Program evaluation is co-led by Anne U. Gold, Megan K. Littrell, and Emily Ward. This study has been approved by the University of Colorado Institutional Research Board (IRB) Protocol 23-0162. Funding for this work was provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF, Award #DBI-2153040). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the NSF.

Executive Summary

Pre-Summit Activities Evaluation

Participants generally found the sessions to be engaging and well-organized, benefiting from the brainstorming activities and networking opportunities, and they saw the sessions as valuable for summit preparation and gathering diverse perspectives. To improve these activities, respondents suggested integrating pre-Summit activities into the main program, offering clear guidelines for team collaboration, providing remote access options (for the in-person activities), including more diverse topics, making certain sessions mandatory, and incorporating interactive elements and visual aids for better engagement and understanding.

ESII Innovation Summit Evaluation

Overall, the ESII Innovation Summit met or exceeded expectations in areas related to networking, collaboration, inclusivity, and diverse discussions. Some participants felt that there could have been more technical content, clearer objectives, and concrete project development during the event.

86% of respondents were **satisfied** with the ESII Innovation Summit overall.

81% of respondents felt that the ESII Innovation Summit was a **good investment of their time**.

80% of respondents indicated that they were **motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS** after the Summit.

Sense of Belonging: Respondents felt a statistically significantly stronger sense of belonging in the EDS community after the Summit compared to before.

Culture of Inclusion: A large majority of respondents agreed that colleagues' contributions were **respected and valued (90-95%)**. There was less consistent agreement that all participants felt **comfortable providing feedback** and contributing **opposing viewpoints (66-73%)**.

Technical support and Cyber infrastructure: Approximately **half of respondents agreed** that they learned about **new technologies and opportunities for data synthesis** and improved their **understanding of cyberinfrastructure**. **67%** agreed that they gained a **broader understanding of data science**. Open-ended responses suggest a greater need for integration of data tools and skills training integrated into the Summit.

Unconference Format: Observations of the event and attendees' survey responses confirmed that the Summit successfully followed the **unconference format** as intended.

Feedback on Virtual Participation in the Summit

92% of respondents agreed that the Summit **facilitation was effective**.

75% of respondents agreed that virtual participants were **included**, had **effective ways to engage** with the Summit, and that the **unconference format worked well** in this environment. There was less agreement (**42%**) that **networking** in the virtual space was effective.

Improvements to Virtual Participation: Virtual attendees expressed feeling somewhat disconnected from those attending in person, highlighting the need for increased interaction between the two groups. Organizers should continue to innovate and share lessons learned to enhance the virtual component and bridge the gap between virtual and in-person participants.

The Best Parts of the ESIL Innovation Summit

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking and Collaboration	Connecting with diverse individuals, collaborating in environmental data science.
Community Building	Fostering a sense of community, emphasizing inclusivity and safe discussions.
Learning and Growth	Expanding knowledge, learning from experts and peers, and stepping out of comfort zones.
Provocative Discussions	Thought-provoking talks on ethical and philosophical aspects of data science.
Event Organization	Well-organized event with structured activities and attention to detail.
Cultural and Indigenous Insights	Appreciation for insights into Indigenous culture and perspectives.
Leadership and Acknowledgment	Recognition of leadership addressing inclusivity and appreciating organizers.
Positive Atmosphere	Providing an open, encouraging environment, accommodating diverse needs.

Respondents' Recommendations for Improvements to the ESIL Innovation Summit

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
Communication and Information Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide clearer information about the Summit's purpose and activities during the application process. • Set clear expectations for participants' Summit accomplishments. • Improve advertising to align with the Summit experience.
Technical Skills and Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use tools and skills learned in pre-Summit training during the Summit. • Offer longer, technical workshops on analytical and computer skills. • Provide more time for hands-on usage of data science tools and platforms.

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
Diversity and Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure better representation of various academic disciplines, especially in social sciences and public health. • Incorporate DEI (Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion) and anti-racist training into the program. • Create an anonymous channel for participants to report inclusivity-related issues.
Team Building and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocate time for team-building activities to foster trust and collaboration. • Facilitate connections between research question groups and relevant resources or individuals. • Promote networking opportunities, both formal and informal.
Summit Structure and Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus more on specific science questions to drive innovation. • Provide more structured and guided activities, especially for group projects. • Offer opportunities to connect with communities outside of participants' own disciplines. • Incorporate more technical aspects into summit activities. • Align pre-Summit training with the Summit's objectives.
Environmental Awareness and Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage composting and sustainable practices during the summit. • Consider the environmental impact of summit activities, such as waste reduction.
Post-Summit Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a clear path forward for teams and projects beyond the summit. • Create an online platform for teams to collaborate and share documents. • Provide resources and support for follow-up work on research questions.
Leadership and Facilitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure more consistent facilitation in group discussions to avoid disruptions. • Consider assigning one facilitator to visit predetermined groups to maintain continuity.
Specific Activities and Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include more diverse flash talks or presentations. • Organize hackathons or data challenges to promote collaboration and innovation. • Showcase innovative projects and research during the summit. • Offer a conflict resolution unit or team to navigate difficult conversations.
Engaging Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve a broader range of stakeholders, including academia, industry, government, nonprofits, and community groups.
Cultural Sensitivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide education on tribal sovereignty for non-tribal participants.

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
Logistics and Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the logistics of venue size and breakout room acoustics to improve communication. • Implement measures to help participants with disabilities or special needs. • Streamline the participant registration process and platform usability.

Accommodations for ESIL Events: Respondents would like for ESIL events to include considerations for physical accessibility and sensory needs (e.g., quiet spaces available) and breaks to allow for information processing, as well as precautions for COVID-19. They appreciate opportunities to work in breakout groups, both in person and online and opportunities for socialization at in-person events. They would also like access to materials after events (e.g., recorded presentations, notes, presentation slides).¹

¹ Icons in the Executive Summary provided by the Noun Project’s creators: Rinaros 79, IconStock, Eko Purnomo, and Siti Nurhayati.

Summit Attendee Characteristics

Summit and Survey Participation

There were 174 respondents for the Summit Pre-Survey (86% response rate) and 137 respondents on the Summit Reflection survey (67% response rate). 86% of the pre-summit survey respondents attended the summit in person and 14% attended virtually. The Summit served an international audience with 91% of respondents reporting that they live in the U.S. (See the figure below for a heat map; Brighter areas represent a higher concentration of attendees) and 9% reporting that they live outside of the U.S. Survey respondents represented attendees from 26 U.S. States and 9 other countries, including Australia, Brazil, Denmark, France, Germany, Romania, Israel, Kenya, and Norway.

Participant Demographic Information

Survey respondents identified as follows: 53% identified as Women, and most others (43%) identified as Men. 3% of respondents identified as Non-binary, Gender non-conforming, or Two-spirit, and less than 1% preferred not to answer. 20% of survey respondents did not complete the demographic questions, which were optional.

Gender Identity	
53%	Women
43%	Men
3%	Non-binary, Gender non-conforming, or two-spirit
<1%	I prefer not to answer

Most respondents identified as White, Caucasian, European, or European American (59%). Participants also identified as Asian or Asian American (11%); Black, African American, or African (7%); American Indian or Alaska Native (5%); Hispanic, Latinx, or Hispanic or Latinx American (4%); or Middle Eastern or North African, Middle Eastern or North African American (3%). 3% of respondents preferred not to answer and 8% picked more than one selection for race or ethnicity.

13% of respondents identified as having a disability or as being neurodiverse; 7% of attendees preferred not to answer this question. 19 % of respondents identified as LGBTQ+; 5% of attendees preferred not to answer this question. Less than 1% of respondents were members of the U.S. Armed Forces. 65% of respondents reported having parents or guardians with a Bachelor’s degree or higher.

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

More than half of the respondents (54%) had earned a doctoral degree, 23% had a Master’s degree, 1% had earned an applied or professional graduate degree (e.g., MD, DDS, JD), and 8% had completed some graduate work. 12% of respondents had earned a Bachelor’s degree, 1% had earned an Associate degree, and 1% had completed some college.

Field of Study: Attendees were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompass a diverse range of academic disciplines, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to its advancement and application.

Race and Ethnicity*

59%	White, Caucasian, European, or European American
11%	Asian or Asian American
7%	Black, African American, or African
5%	American Indian or Alaska Native
4%	Hispanic, Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
3%	I prefer not to answer
3%	Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
1%	Other
8%	More than one selection

Highest Level of Education

54%	Doctoral degree
23%	Master’s degree
12%	Bachelor’s degree
8%	Some graduate work
1%	Applied or professional graduate degree
1%	Associate degree
1%	Some college

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Atmospheric Science	Aeronautics/ Astronautics Engineering	Anthropology	Public Health
Biogeochemistry	Applied Mathematics	Communication Studies	Statistics
Biology	Biomedical Science	Crisis Informatics	Theoretical Physics
Botany	Biotechnology	Education	

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Earth System Science	Computer Science	Environmental Data Science	
Ecology	Geological Engineering	Environmental Management	
Environmental Science	Operations Research	Lakota Studies	
Environmental Toxicology		Law	
Geology		Library Science	
Hydrology		Policy and Management	
Marine Science		Science Management	
Marine Biology		Sociology	
Physics			
Plant Breeding and Genetics			
Soil Science			
Wildlife and Conservation Biology			

Career Stage: The majority of respondents (54%) described themselves as Early Career (0 – 5 years of professional experience or a student or post-doctoral fellow). 30% were Mid-Career (6 – 15 years of professional experience) and 15% were at a Senior stage in their career (more than 15 years of experience).

Affiliation: The majority of respondents reported that they work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (73%)**, followed by **Non-profit organizations (18%)**, and **Federal Government agencies (10%)**. Only 1 – 2% reported working for Local or State government agencies, Private for-profit organizations, industry positions, or in K-12 or Informal Education. 4% of respondents chose “Other” with responses including Indigenous or Tribal institutions, including Tribal colleges and the American Indian Higher Education Consortium (“AIHEC”), a “Consortium of representatives of biological collections,” and “Intergovernmental (IGO)”.

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a Research-Intensive institution (74%). 37% of academic affiliations included institutions serving both undergraduate and graduate students and 5% served primarily undergraduates. 3% of academic affiliations included Professional Programs. Some respondents also reported affiliation with a Minority-serving Institution (7%); a Hispanic-serving institution (13%); a Tribal College or Tribal-serving institution (8%); or an American or Native American Pacific Islander-serving institution (3%). Note that there were no respondents affiliated with Community Colleges or Historically Black Colleges and Universities. Additional written responses included “Botanical Gardens,” “Data Science organization within a university;” “National Lab,” “Research Center” or “Research Institute,” and “German University.”

Types of Academic Affiliations*	
74%	Research Intensive
37%	Undergraduate & Graduate students
5%	Undergraduate students
3%	Professional Programs
13%	Hispanic-Serving Institution
8%	Tribal College or University
7%	Minority-Serving Institution
3%	American or Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution

*Respondents selected all that apply. Percentages add up to more than 100%.

Non-Academic Affiliations. Respondents who *do not* work for an academic institution described the main organization they are affiliated with, which were grouped in four different non-academic affiliations:

Government Agencies, Labs, and Contractors	Non-Profit and NGO Sector	Research and Education Sector	Private Sector
Department of Energy user facilities	American Indian organizations	Institutions for applied science on conservation	Consultancy companies
Earth & space science agencies	Consortium of Tribal Colleges and Universities	Institutions funded by NSF	Geospatial data providers
Federal land-management agencies	Environmental non-profits	National observatories	Publicly traded for-profit companies
Federal research agencies	NGOs funded through NSF	Research teams of environmental non-profits	
Federally funded research and development centers	Non-profit observatories/lab operations and management		
Government contractors	Organizations improving data resources		
National laboratories			

Primary role in the Environmental Data Science (EDS) Field:

Summit attendees were asked to choose their primary roles in the broad field of EDS. Researchers (43%) represented the largest group at the Summit with smaller percentages of people who primarily identified as a Student (18%), a Director or Program Manager (11%), or indicated that they had a role that was not listed (Other, 14%). Other roles respondents wrote in included the following categories:

- Administrative and leadership roles (e.g., Co-lead
- Co-lead working groups;
- Community Engagement;
- Data roles (Data Manager, officer, provider, user support);
- Editor in Chief;
- Engaging Tribal communities in EDS ("Bringing EDS to Indian Country," "Tribal Liaison," "Tribal citizen trying to find tools to adapt to climate change");
- Observer;
- PhD candidate;
- Program and Project Management (Project developer, Program Coordinator, Program Assistant);
- Software Developer; and
- Team Science.

Disciplinary fields in EDS: The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (68%)**, **Computer/Data Science (43%)**, **Biological Science (38%)**, and **Geoscience (24%)**. Fewer respondents represented Engineering (9%) and Math (9%) and Economics (3%). The majority of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Open-ended "Other" responses (13%) included: "applying science for planning and adaptation," Atmospheric Science; Convergence Science; Ecology; "Ecosystem and innovation management," Education and teaching; Environmental Health; Ethics and Indigenous Data Sovereignty; Geoinformatics; Land Use; Ocean Science; and Statistics; and Traditional Ecological Knowledge.

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships comprises a wide range of professional societies, including those related to natural sciences, social sciences, mathematics, ecology, geophysics, biology, geography, and more. Some societies are discipline-specific (e.g., American Mathematical Society, Ecological Society of America), while others are more broadly focused on fields like geophysics, earth sciences, and data science. Additionally, there are some societies dedicated to supporting underrepresented groups (e.g., American Indian Science and Engineering Society, SACNAS) and promoting diversity in STEM. Several societies

(e.g., American Geophysical Union and the Ecological Society of America) appeared multiple times in the list, indicating their prominence and potential popularity among professionals.

Accommodations for Attendees

On the pre-survey, attendees were asked to describe accommodations needed to make ESIIIL events as accessible as possible. Ten attendees provided responses to this question. Below is a summary of themes and representative verbatim quotes.

COVID Precautions and Sensory Considerations:

- "I would appreciate some level of covid precautions -- open windows, acceptance of those who choose to wear N95 masks, options to eat and meet with others outside"
- "A lot of sound in an enclosed space or other sensory stimuli can be overwhelming, so as long as there is a quiet space I can retreat to for a few moments when needed..."
- "The room was a little loud at a few points, which was a good thing! But it was overstimulating at times and some others who have a hard time speaking up may have struggled saying anything."

Processing and Breaks:

- "I sometimes get 'full' and need to leave the room to process information."
- "I do best with breaks and structure. It also helps me to know what to expect, I don't do well with surprises."

Access to Materials:

- "recorded lectures and/or notes from the in-person sessions"

Mobility and Physical Considerations:

- "Mobility considerations for crutch users"

Parenting and Timing:

- "As a parent of a pre-schooler, it is difficult to attend events outside of normal working hours. I appreciate that the main activities...are scheduled at midday rather than evenings/weekends, as well as the zoom options."

Breakout Sessions and Structured Format:

- "If in person, more breakout sessions outside or in separate rooms. If virtual, breakout rooms are always nice."

Curiosity about Social Activities:

- "Wondering if there would be any trip/hiking activities!"

Attendees' Personal Summit Goals

On the Summit pre-survey, attendees shared 1-3 personal goals they had for the Summit. Common themes in their responses are summarized below. These themes highlight participants' diverse motivations, ranging from skill development and career growth to community engagement, advocacy, and advancing environmental research through data science.

- **Learning and Skill Development:** Participants aim to expand their data science knowledge and technical skills in areas like coding, data analysis, and software tools.

- **Networking and Collaboration:** Building professional relationships and finding collaboration opportunities with like-minded individuals are key objectives for participants.
- **Understanding the Field:** Participants seek insights into current trends, challenges, and applications of data science in environmental issues.
- **Application of Data Science:** Participants want to explore how data science can be used to address environmental challenges and inform decision-making.
- **Community Building:** Some participants prioritize creating a diverse and inclusive community within the environmental data science field.
- **Awareness and Education:** Participants aim to promote open data and accessibility in environmental science while sharing knowledge and ideas.
- **Specific Interests and Projects:** Some participants have specific research interests they hope to advance or find support for.
- **Supporting Indigenous and Tribal Interests:** Engaging with Indigenous knowledge, data sovereignty, and environmental justice is a focus for certain participants.
- **Professional and Career Development:** Participants are looking to identify job opportunities, gain exposure, and acquire new skills in the field.
- **Contributing to ESILL's Mission:** Many participants express a desire to contribute to ESILL's mission and vision during and after the summit.

Participation in Pre-Summit Activities

Prior to the Summit, the leadership team engaged Summit attendees in optional Pre-Summit activities, including brainstorming sessions to identify topics and activities the attendees desired to address at the Summit; technical training sessions, and training sessions on leadership, cultural intelligence, tribal engagement, and scientific collaboration.

47% of the Summit pre-survey respondents participated in the pre-Summit brainstorming sessions. They shared feedback on these sessions, including:

- Participants generally found the sessions to be engaging and well-organized, benefiting from the brainstorming activities and networking opportunities, and they saw the sessions as valuable for summit preparation and gathering diverse perspectives. However, some respondents felt uncertain about goals and faced technical challenges. Breakout groups received mixed feedback, with some finding them productive while others noted challenges. Toward improving these activities, participants suggested more time, clearer instructions, and providing real-life examples.

95% of Summit Reflection survey respondents reported engaging in the Pre-Summit activities, with:

- **48%** participating in the Pre-Summit Brainstorming Sessions
- **56%** participating in the Leadership and Collaboration Pre-Summit Activities (day before Summit)
- **72%** participating in the Technical Trainings for Collaboration in Environmental Data Science

On the Summit Reflection survey, attendees were also asked to rate how useful each of the trainings were and how well the technical trainings prepared them for the Summit, summarized in the graphs below. The majority

of respondents agreed that trainings on leadership and collaboration were useful to them. Regarding technical training, a large majority of respondents agreed the training on the KIstorm platform was beneficial. Approximately half of respondents agreed that the tools for open and reproducible science training prepared them for the Summit. There was less agreement for other tools (with 37 to 48% agreeing and 20 -26% disagreeing) including R & Python bilingualism, cloud-based computing workstations, and the Cyverse Discovery Environment. Attendees' recommendations for improvement of pre-Summit activities are listed below.

Leadership and Collaboration Pre-Summit Activities

Technical Trainings for Collaboration in Environmental Data Science

[Respondents' Recommendation for Improving Pre-Summit Activities and Technical Trainings](#)

Respondents' recommendations for improving the Pre-Summit Activities include the following themes:

- **Integration and Continuity with the Main Event:**
 - Integrate Pre-Summit Activities into the main Summit program rather than keeping them separate, making attendance more justifiable and ensuring that the valuable content is not missed by participants who couldn't attend the Pre-Summit.
 - Clearly communicate the link between Pre-Summit and Summit Activities to set expectations.
- **Content and Format Enhancements:**
 - Provide clear guidelines on how to collaborate better in teams.
 - Offer specific action items and practical takeaways in sessions to help participants apply what they've learned.
- **Accessibility and Remote Participation:**
 - Provide remote access options for participants who are unable to attend in person, allowing them to watch talks in real-time and ask questions remotely.
 - Ensure better documentation pages for all activities and make recordings or slide decks available for reflection and reference.
- **Inclusivity and Relevance:**
 - Include topics related to biodiversity, socio-ecological and environmental data from the global south, addressing the needs of diverse regions.
 - Make certain sessions (e.g., Cultural Intelligence and Tribal Engagement) mandatory to ensure that all participants benefit from the knowledge and insights shared.
- **Interactive and Hands-On Learning:**
 - Incorporate more interactive and hands-on elements, such as workshops or training sessions, to enhance participant engagement and practical skill development.
 - Create visual aids or diagrams to illustrate the various contributors to EDS and professions in related fields, helping participants better understand their roles and contributions.

Respondents' recommendations for improving the Technical trainings include the following themes:

- **Alignment with Summit Activities:**
 - Participants expressed that they expected to use certain tools, like Jupyter notebooks and CyVerse, during the summit but didn't get the opportunity. They suggested incorporating activities with these tools into the summit or future events to make the training more practical.
 - Some participants suggested that technical training modules could be more relevant as post-summit follow-ups when participants start analyzing data or working on projects.
- **Clarity and Accessibility:**
 - Many participants found the pace of the technical training modules to be fast, especially for those with limited technical skills. They recommended providing a primer on basic technical jargon and concepts to help participants better understand the content.
 - Clearer communication of the time commitment and a list of websites/tools to be used would be helpful for participants to prepare adequately.
- **Structuring and Delivery:**

- Some participants recommended structuring the technical training modules more effectively, possibly by providing learning objectives and ensuring a more organized presentation.
- Participants also mentioned that pre-recorded sessions with opportunities for participants to follow along at their own pace could be beneficial, especially for those who cannot attend live sessions.

Summit Evaluation Outcomes

Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL Innovation Summit

86% of respondents were **satisfied** with the ESIL Innovation Summit overall (42% “Strongly Agree;” 44% “Agree”).

81% of respondents felt that the ESIL Innovation Summit was a **good investment of their time** (27% “Extremely well invested.” 54% “Well invested”).

The majority of respondents agreed that the various components of the Summit agenda were effective (e.g., Speed Networking, Provocations, Breakout Groups, Community Discussions, Reflections, Social activities). They also overall agreed that the Summit was well-organized, engaging, and facilitated opportunities for networking and collaboration.

Feedback on Virtual Participation in the Summit

A large majority of participants in the virtual Summit agreed that the facilitation was done well (92%), virtual participants were included (75%) and they had effective ways to engage with the Summit (75%), and that they unconference format worked well in this environment (75%). There was less agreement (42%) that networking in the virtual space was effective.

Suggestions for Improvement of Virtual Participation

The feedback from virtual participants at the ESIL Innovation Summit varied, with some expressing appreciation for the experience and others highlighting areas for improvement. Overall, the virtual participants reported feeling somewhat disconnected from the in-person attendees. To enhance future virtual participation, respondents suggested encouraging more interaction between both groups.

Summit Overall Highlights

The best parts of the ESIL Innovation Summit, according to respondents, can be summarized into the following key themes:

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking and Collaboration	Connecting with diverse individuals, collaborating in environmental data science.
Community Building	Fostering a sense of community, emphasizing inclusivity and safe discussions.
Learning and Growth	Expanding knowledge, learning from experts and peers, and stepping out of comfort zones.
Provocative Discussions	Thought-provoking talks on ethical and philosophical aspects of data science.
Event Organization	Well-organized event with structured activities and attention to detail.
Cultural and Indigenous Insights	Appreciation for insights into Indigenous culture and perspectives.
Leadership and Acknowledgment	Recognition of leadership addressing inclusivity and appreciating organizers.
Positive Atmosphere	Providing an open, encouraging environment, accommodating diverse needs.

Themes from the responses regarding to what extent the Innovation Summit met participants' expectations and where it fell short can be summarized as follows:

Met Expectations:

- **Networking and Community Building:** Many participants expressed satisfaction with the networking opportunities and the chance to connect with a diverse range of individuals from different fields, fostering collaboration and new relationships.
- **Diverse Perspectives:** Participants appreciated the diversity of perspectives present at the summit, which led to stimulating discussions and creative insights.
- **Community and Collaboration:** The summit successfully promoted community building and collaborative efforts, with participants working together on projects and ideas.
- **Inclusivity:** The summit exceeded expectations in terms of inclusivity, featuring diverse voices, including Native American perspectives, and fostering discussions around cultural intelligence.
- **Provocative Discussions:** Attendees found the discussions thought-provoking and appreciated the opportunity to engage in high-level brainstorming sessions on environmental data science challenges.

Did Not Meet Expectations:

- **Technical Content:** Some participants were hoping for more technical content, including coding and hands-on activities related to data science tools and platforms like CyVerse.
- **Concrete Outputs:** Some participants expected more concrete outcomes, such as specific project development, deliverables, and actionable plans emerging from the discussions.

- **Clarity of Objectives:** Several participants expressed uncertainty about the specific objectives of the summit, leading to confusion about the goals and direction of the event.
- **Balancing Science and Social Aspects:** While many appreciated the social and cultural discussions, some attendees felt that there was less focus on technical aspects and hands-on coding than expected.
- **International Participation:** There were comments indicating that the network was predominantly focused on the USA, and some participants expected more international representation.
- **Concrete Plans and Funding:** Some participants were looking for more concrete plans for the future, including funding opportunities and support for ongoing collaboration.

In a final open-ended question, respondents shared the additional feedback on the ESIL Innovator Summit. Themes and representative verbatim responses are included below:

Positive Feedback:

- **Gratitude and Appreciation:**
 - "I enjoyed the summit and learned a lot. Thank you for organizing it!"
 - "Bravo - a great way to kick off the start of what will hopefully be a thriving and vibrant community. Thanks for making it FUN!"
 - "It was a very valuable experience and I remain grateful for the opportunity to be part of it."
 - "Thanks so much for organizing the summit! There's so much potential in the summit and I'm looking forward to how it develops in future years."
- **Networking and Connections:**
 - "The people I met and the connections that have been created will be long-lasting and generate many collaborations."
 - "I had the opportunity to connect with people outside my discipline, people with expertise I've been looking for but haven't know how to connect with; this is exactly the role I think a synthesis center should be serving in the community."
 - "It was very exciting to attend the Innovation Summit, establish new contacts to future projects and know the amazing Boulder."
- **Inclusivity and Diversity:**
 - "I appreciate that the ESIL group really put the inclusive piece at the forefront. It is a challenge, but we won't make any progress without this kind of consistent and persistent effort."
 - "I really appreciate the intentional mix of people/expertise/identities ESIL brought to the Summit. It set us up for difficult and important conversations while fostering a growth mindset and giving everyone space to feel supported while being challenged."
 - "I appreciate the novelty and inclusive practices in your approach to building an EDS community."
- **Effort of Organizers:**
 - "The organizing team deserves a huge round of applause. The pre-Summit activities, resources, activities, and keeping everything running smoothly must have required a tremendous effort, but for such a complex event to run so well is a huge achievement."
 - "The Summit was extremely well designed and well-coordinated."
 - "[The facilitators] were very welcoming, it was appreciated!"
- **Desire for Further Involvement:**

- "I'm looking forward to future events that were teased at the summit, such as hackathons."
- "I hope it's a resilient community and do wish [for] continuous participation."
- "I would like to be part of EDS community via ESILL moving forward. Many of the goals align with mine as I move into retirement."
- "I'd be happy to collaborate, will follow the calls for working groups etc."

Negative Feedback:

- **Lack of Clarity Around "EDS" terminology:**

- "I suppose I don't have a clear idea of what the 'EDS community' is...maybe I should by now."
- "I strongly identify with environmental data science, not so much with earth data science (which to me is more about physical systems than biological ones). I think ESILL has been vacillating between the two terms and it would be great to see more clarity."

- **Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Issues:**

- "There were some issues with DEI. I really appreciated the attempts made to be inclusive, but we really needed to be talking about the actual issues that the Indigenous community raised."
- "I would have appreciated more transparency about the harm that occurred to our Indigenous participants."
- "There were several problematic aspects of the Team Science presentation. One was a statement generalizing Women in science teams (I can't see the video online to get the actual quote), another was a research question about investigating socio-cultural diversity effects on team science. This could lead to tokenizing and generalizing whole groups of people based on their identity. Lastly, by using productivity as a metric of "success" we are perpetuating an inequitable structure in academia that harms historically marginalized peoples in science."

- **Length of Survey:**

- "[T]his survey is too long."
- "Survey was too long..."

- **Inclusion of All Fields and Partners in ESILL's Community**

- "The Summit emphasized to me that this is an academic research group. Coming from a government perspective, I can be a partner, I can communicate our needs, I can work toward solutions, but I don't particularly feel like a part of the community."
- "Oceanography and ocean-related topics were never directly included in the sessions. There are enough parallels where some high-level topics could relate but it was challenging to find direct applications of a lot of content to my research field. It would be great to include an ocean-focused theme in addition to the ones on fire, precipitation, hazards, land use, sustainable development, etc."

- **Broad vs. More Specific Focus**

- "I think ESILL's mission is extremely important and I'm sorry to be rather negative in my feedback. For a very broad group like this, training in interdisciplinary collaboration/team science and on computational technical skills seem like the two areas that would have best served the needs/wants of the participants from my perspective. I feel like smaller and more consciously assembled groups (especially that can work against the clustering in terms of discipline and background, and also that include some members with deep expertise) would be

more effective toward the innovation goals than the sometimes-too-large and frequently changing breakout groups.”

- “I think the most difficult thing was choosing a particular question to focus on because most people wanted to keep things broad. I think many groups were caught up in that.”

Areas for Improvement

Summit participants recommended the following improvements for future Summits:

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
Communication and Information Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide clearer information about the Summit's purpose and activities during the application process. • Set clear expectations for participants' Summit accomplishments. • Improve advertising to align with the Summit experience.
Technical Skills and Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use tools and skills learned in pre-Summit training during the Summit. • Offer longer, technical workshops on analytical and computer skills. • Provide more time for hands-on usage of data science tools and platforms.
Diversity and Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure better representation of various academic disciplines, especially in social sciences and public health. • Incorporate DEI (Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion) and anti-racist training into the program. • Create an anonymous channel for participants to report inclusivity-related issues.
Team Building and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocate time for team-building activities to foster trust and collaboration. • Facilitate connections between research question groups and relevant resources or individuals. • Promote networking opportunities, both formal and informal.
Summit Structure and Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus more on specific science questions to drive innovation. • Provide more structured and guided activities, especially for group projects. • Offer opportunities to connect with communities outside of participants' own disciplines. • Incorporate more technical aspects into summit activities. • Align pre-Summit training with the Summit's objectives.
Environmental Awareness and Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage composting and sustainable practices during the summit. • Consider the environmental impact of summit activities, such as waste reduction.
Post-Summit Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a clear path forward for teams and projects beyond the summit.

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create an online platform for teams to collaborate and share documents. • Provide resources and support for follow-up work on research questions.
Leadership and Facilitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure more consistent facilitation in group discussions to avoid disruptions. • Consider assigning one facilitator to visit predetermined groups to maintain continuity.
Specific Activities and Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include more diverse flash talks or presentations. • Organize hackathons or data challenges to promote collaboration and innovation. • Showcase innovative projects and research during the summit. • Offer a conflict resolution unit or team to navigate difficult conversations.
Engaging Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve a broader range of stakeholders, including academia, industry, government, nonprofits, and community groups.
Cultural Sensitivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide education on tribal sovereignty for non-tribal participants.
Logistics and Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the logistics of venue size and breakout room acoustics to improve communication. • Implement measures to help participants with disabilities or special needs. • Streamline the participant registration process and platform usability.

Evaluation of Breakout Group Work

80% of respondents indicated that they were **motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS** after the Summit.

A majority of respondents agreed that breakout groups gathered **enthusiastic collaborators (85%)**, **brainstorming was effective (70%)**, and groups were able to **develop project plans (60%)** and **outlines (56%)**. There was less agreement that groups **developed plans to collaborate beyond the Summit (45%)** and that **collaboration seemed feasible (42%)**.

Suggestions for Improvement of Breakout Group Work

- **Clarity of Purpose:** Some participants found it challenging to grasp the objectives and scope of the breakout groups, with some feeling that topics were overly broad, slide templates didn't align with available tools, and more guidance on outcomes was needed.
- **Group Dynamics:** Concerns included too-large or too-small group sizes, a few dominating individuals, and possibly exclusionary communication issues like unclear language and high-level terminology.
- **Diversity and Inclusivity:** Some participants noted tensions between different perspectives, such as those focused on decolonial approaches and those representing data-centric viewpoints. Concerns were raised about a lack of Indigenous participants in groups addressing Indigenous issues.
- **Time Management:** Some participants felt there was insufficient time for idea development and suggested incorporating breaks or workshops for better structure.
- **Topic Feedback:** Some participants desired more technology-related guidance or group members with expertise in areas like data science/AI, some would have preferred focusing on identifying knowledge “gaps” over the focus on innovation, and some found the topics too ambitious.
- **Continued Collaboration:** Participants wanted projects initiated during the Summit to continue and a lack of time and resources for outlining future projects and collaborations was noted.
- **Positive Feedback:** Despite challenges, numerous participants expressed enthusiasm and appreciation for the breakout groups and the event overall.

Evaluation of Technical Support and Cyberinfrastructure

Approximately **half of respondents agreed** that they learned about **new technologies and opportunities for data synthesis** and improved their **understanding of cyberinfrastructure**.

67% agreed that they gained a **broader understanding of data science**.

Evaluation of the Unconference Format

The Summit was designed following the common elements of an “unconference” style meeting (Budd et al., 2015). Survey items and observations of the Summit conducted by three evaluators focused on the following six broad design elements of an unconference style meeting.

- There are opportunities for participants to directly influence what is happening at the summit (e.g., through topics, presentations, sharing of interest and expertise).
- The discussions and engagement in the breakout groups appear relevant for attendees.
- There is an emphasis on contributions from every participant and facilitation is inclusive and welcoming regardless of how experienced they are (“no idea is too trivial”).
- The summit atmosphere is relaxed, open, friendly, fun, and welcoming (inclusive of newcomers and those new to EDS).
- Participants learn about useful skills or tools related to EDS, or they applied skills and tools to EDS work.
- There are opportunities for and encouragement of collaborative work and interactive knowledge exchange/transdisciplinary work.

Summit attendees provided feedback on the Unconference Style format:

Inclusive and Welcoming of Ideas: As illustrated in the figure below, a large majority of survey respondents (**89% - 92%**) agreed that the **Summit was inclusive and welcomed contributions and ideas from all participants**, regardless of background experience, and that the atmosphere was relaxed and friendly.

Collaboration and Networking: A large majority of respondents (**80 – 82%**) agreed that the Summit offered adequate opportunities for **transdisciplinary collaboration and networking, relevant breakout group activities**, and was **welcoming** for newcomers to the field.

Participant Influence: **77%** of respondents also agreed that there were **opportunities to directly influence** what was happening each day at the Summit.

Application of Skills or Tools: Less than half of respondents (**44%**) agreed that they had **learned about and/or applied useful skills or tools** related to EDS at the Summit, with 20% giving a neutral response and 35% expressing disagreement.

Results from Observations of the Summit Unconference Format and Evidence of the Implementation

Context: Three evaluation team members recorded observations at the meeting, following the six broad design elements of unconference-style meetings. Two observers attended the pre-Summit virtual sessions and trainings. One observer attended all Summit events in person and served as a mentor for Summit attendees. One observer also attended in person on the first day of the summit and virtually for the remaining days. A third observer also joined the Summit virtually on Days 2 and 3.

Locations:

- The in-person meeting took place in a large Auditorium room at the University of Colorado SEEC research building with round tables and large sheets of butcher paper on the walls to capture discussions notes around Challenges and Opportunities and the Research Questions. In addition, large butcher paper was provided to share Community Challenges and Needs and sign-up for the Soap box timeslots. The building layout allowed groups to spread out into smaller rooms and also sit outside in a quiet courtyard. Food was provided just outside the main meeting area.

- Zoom participants were connected via a good audio and projection system. Facilitation was provided for the zoom session. Provocations were recorded and also streamed. Breakout groups on Day 1 happened online only. Starting on Day 2 when the group worked on research questions, some groups operated in a hybrid mode by zooming in virtual participants.

Communication:

- The KI Storm App was the digital tool that contained the agenda and allowed for access of working documents.
- An ESIL Summit Slack Channel provided online communication opportunities.
- A Twitter Hashtag (@CU_ESIL) and an Instagram (@cu_esil) was shared and participants were encouraged to share about the Summit on social media.

Participatory Elements in Summit Agenda and Observation Themes: The agenda of the Summit and Pre-Summit activities included various participatory components. The Pre-Summit Activities in the weeks prior to the Summit happened virtually, and the trainings on the day before the Summit were offered in person. The Summit agenda focused on the in-person participants but a parallel agenda with the same content blocks were offered for Zoom virtual attendees. Participation in the Zoom sessions declined throughout the day and throughout the Summit.

Observation Theme 1: *There are opportunities for participants to directly influence what is happening at the summit (e.g., through topics, presentations, sharing of interest and expertise).*

Pre-Summit

- The Summit's content agenda was shaped by participant input, with over 600 EDS challenges and opportunities submitted and condensed into 67 themes by the ESIL leadership team. During two virtual pre-summit brainstorming sessions, separate groups of summit participants collaborated to further group and prioritize the themes through use of the *Well-sorted App* and discussion. Participants paired down the 67 themes into 10 broader themes, which were then further synthesized by the leadership team into 16 key discussion topics for Summit breakout groups. This process fostered deep attendee engagement in shaping the Summit agenda.

During the Summit

- Sharing of Hopes and Fears about the Summit and discussing how to address fears appeared to create a feeling of connection at the full group session and supported the notion that participants were able to contribute to the arc of the Summit.
- Agenda goals were very broad and through the presentation of this high level, the facilitators implied that the agenda was somewhat flexible.
- Having two groups form around each theme and research question allowed participants to self-select the direction they wanted to take and select the team to work with.
- Share-outs throughout the Summit gave voice to participants and provided the stage to share contributions.
- Soapbox presentations provided an opportunity for participants to share topics with the entire Summit community.
- The shift in agenda on the last day (though not driven by participants but by the leadership team) demonstrated that the agenda was flexible and adjustable.

- Formation of the affinity groups on Day 2 showed that the leadership team was responsive to the interest of attendees.

Observation Theme 2: *The discussions and engagement in the breakout groups appear relevant for attendees.*

- Discussions throughout the different breakout groups appeared vibrant and engaged.
- Breakout groups appeared powerful in elevating voices and asking people to contribute and ensure contributions for everyone.
- The ability of participants to self-select into the different breakout groups, encouraged participants to select topics they were personally interested in.
- The agenda provided multiple opportunities for participants to switch groups and select the topic that was most relevant to them. This also provided attendees with ample opportunities for networking and sharing ideas with multiple participants.
- However, facilitation in each group was left to the groups themselves. While general guidance was given on inclusivity, the self-organized facilitation resulted in a few groups having some participants dominate the conversation and others contributing less.
- Affinity groups introduced on Day 2 allowed for meaningful conversation with like-minded people. These affinity groups met for a long time and their facilitators reported very meaningful discussions.

Observation Theme 3: There is an emphasis on *contributions from every participant* and facilitation is inclusive and welcoming of everyone in attendance (“*no idea is too trivial*”).

- The Code of Conduct and the clear commitment of the leadership team to the values of inclusivity and a welcoming atmosphere were introduced on the first day and reiterated throughout the Summit.
- The presence of the Diversity expert from the ESIL leadership provided ongoing reminders for inclusivity.
- Tribal ESIL partners’ voices were elevated in the Opening Remarks and the Provocations, as well as through other contributions from Tribal community members (e.g., Soap Box talks, Share outs).
- Day 2 began with remarks from leadership acknowledging feedback from participants and highlighting the need to improve the language on some prompts to be respectful of Tribal community perspectives. This set the stage for more inclusive and respectful conversations.
- Assignment of attendees to their initial round table discussion groups on Day 1 was done with intention. Each group included participants from different career stages and backgrounds in order to foster networking across disciplines and career stages. This intentional group assignment set the stage for the Summit that a variety of voices were important and encouraged.
- Throughout the Summit, facilitators encouraged inclusive conversations. During a provocation, an example from a different synthesis center was shared—in this scenario the junior members of a working group introduced a very innovative research question, but the senior members of the group were dismissive of the idea. However, the group decided to follow through with this question and were very successful. This example helped set the stage for equal contributions and respect from all members of breakout groups regardless of prior experience.
- The NSF program managers and other more senior scientists encouraged everyone to reach out to and interact.

Observation Theme 4: *The summit atmosphere is relaxed, open, friendly, fun, and welcoming (including newcomers and those new to EDS).*

- The Summit space was set up as a collaborative space at round tables with opportunities for small breakout groups and working outside.
- Coloring pens, fidget toys, and art supplies were provided at each table.
- The Code of Conduct presentation and ESILL engagement norms were centered at the beginning of the Summit, providing a supportive and inclusive environment where everyone was encouraged to take care of their needs throughout the Summit.
- *Fears and Hopes* discussion (Day 1) elevated voices from everyone.
- Good food was provided breakfast and lunch and a buffet style eating encouraged networking and connections. This included options for varied dietary needs (e.g., common food allergens listed; vegan options). Lunch was scheduled after the breakout sessions, allowing participants to continue conversations.
- The facilitation of the Summit was engaging, dynamic, and inclusive. Talks were short and the focus was on interaction.
- Summit Attendees were laughing and interacting a lot.
- Affinity groups were offered after the second day.
- Social events (brewery and NEON tour) were offered for participants to connect.

Observation Theme 5: *Participants learn about useful skills or tools related to EDS or they applied skills and tools.*

- The Pre-Summit trainings offered skills trainings.
- A presentation about the available data tools and the data library encouraged participants to access pre-curated data sets.
- Office hours with Cyverse were offered to introduce participants to the infrastructure.
- Despite these various offerings, no group worked with EDS data or applied any new skills.

Observation Theme 6: *There are opportunities for and encouragement of collaborative work and interactive knowledge exchange/transdisciplinary work.*

- Speakers encouraged interactions among attendees and transdisciplinary work.
- Initial group assignments were made to intentionally foster collaboration and transdisciplinary work.
- The research questions and breakout group assignments were set up as transdisciplinary challenges.
- The Summit design was set up to foster collaboration (large round tables, group work etc.).
- The discussions fostered knowledge transfer and sharing of ideas.
- Challenge discussion (Day 3) was centered on challenges, most of which require collaboration and transdisciplinary work.

Observation Theme 7: *Other relevant observations*

- Participants seemed unsure about how the event would unfold and how to contribute on Day 1. However, the facilitator guided participants through the process. The agenda change on Day 3 appeared for some participants to be a surprise as they had wanted to connect with their groups again.

Sense of Belonging in the EDS Community

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to evaluate changes in attendee's the pre-survey and reflection survey responses about sense of belonging. There were 97 respondents with matched pre- and post-responses included in the analysis.

Before and after the Summit, attendees were asked to choose the picture that best described their "the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional." Results showed a significant change such **that attendees saw a greater overlap between themselves and EDS professionals at the end of the Summit** compared to before the Summit, $Z = -4.99$, $p < .001$.

Attendees were also asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements about their sense of belonging in the EDS community. There was a **significant increase** in respondents' agreement with **"I belong to the EDS Community"** ($Z = -5.65, p < .001$) and with **"Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity"** ($Z = -3.09, p = .002$), shown in the figure below.

Culture of Inclusion: General Respect and Respect for Expertise

A large majority of respondents agreed that **colleagues' contributions were respected and valued (90-95%)**. There was less consistent agreement that all participants **felt comfortable providing feedback and contributing opposing viewpoints (66-73%)**.

Summit Outcomes: Overall Impacts and Innovation

A subset of open-ended questions was asked only of the ESIIIL leadership team, Advisory board members, and Summit breakout group leaders. There were 5 respondents for these questions. Responses are summarized below:

Impacts of the ESIIIL Innovation Summit Over the Next 6 Months

Respondents foresee several significant outcomes over the next six months. There is a strong emphasis on community engagement and collaboration, with a recognition that the summit will lead to increased interaction, new partnerships, and the formation of novel collaborative pairs. Moreover, the summit is expected to foster deeper connectivity between ESIIIL and external organizations, potentially amplifying its impact. A notable theme is the intention to translate the summit's discussions into tangible outcomes, such as

the creation of perspective pieces on Innovation and Inclusion in Open Science, as well as the initiation of working group proposal development. Overall, the anticipation is that the summit will not only spur immediate networking but also lay the groundwork for sustained and fruitful long-term collaborations.

[Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit on Innovation](#)

Respondents believe that the ESIL Innovation Summit will drive innovation through various avenues. These include harnessing emerging technologies in unique ways, forging new collaborations with novel value propositions, and addressing inclusion concerns to build future trust. The summit's potential to bring together dedicated individuals passionate about advancing the subject and promoting subsequent contact and collaboration is highlighted. Additionally, the summit is anticipated to elevate ESIL's visibility within the broader environmental, sustainability, and tribal communities. Notably, sustained engagement among diverse individuals with common goals but differing expertise and methodologies is emphasized as crucial for fostering innovation, focusing on the duration and intensity of these interactions.

[Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit on a Decadal EDS Research Agenda](#)

The ESIL Innovation Summit participants are optimistic about its potential to influence a decade-long research roadmap for EDS by fostering new partnerships, expanding inclusive expertise, introducing fresh research value propositions, and recognizing emerging yet critical subject areas. However, the Summit's ultimate impact relies heavily on effectively communicating and following through with the concepts presented by various breakout teams. This event is also viewed as a platform for encouraging collaboration across diverse disciplines and tackling intricate issues, such as socio-cultural integration. Ethical considerations and principles of practice emerge as significant focal points, especially in relation to Indigenous data sovereignty. Participants are keen on finding ways to reconcile or bridge the disparities between Indigenous data ownership and the requirements of open science. In summary, the Summit is anticipated to shape the research agenda for EDS through the facilitation of collaboration, the identification of emerging areas of interest, and the addressing of ethical and interdisciplinary challenges, provided that the ideas generated during the event are effectively communicated and pursued.

The following open-ended questions were asked of all survey respondents. 93 attendees responded to these questions. Responses are summarized below:

[Impacts of the Summit Toward Advancing the field of EDS](#)

Several themes emerge regarding how the ESIL Innovation Summit advanced the field of EDS. Representative verbatim responses are included below each theme.

Inclusivity and Diversity: Many participants emphasized the importance of inclusivity and diversity in advancing EDS. They noted that the Summit placed a strong emphasis on these principles:

- "Emphasis on stakeholder inclusion, data sovereignty and respect for indigenous groups."
- "I think the focus was mostly on diversity, equity, and inclusion which is important."

Community Building: The summit was successful in creating a sense of community within EDS, bringing together individuals from diverse backgrounds:

- "I think the Innovation Summit began the hard work of building a community that has shared values and goals for the field of EDS."
- "Brought the community together to start working through the challenging social changes necessary to truly move the field forward inclusively."

Ethical Considerations: Participants recognized the importance of ethical frameworks in Earth Data Science:

- "Respecting Indigenous Data Science in a very visible way."
- "Developing shared ethical frameworks is absolutely critical."

Awareness and Education: The summit raised awareness of challenges and opportunities in Earth Data Science and provided educational opportunities:

- "I think it started very important conversations and offered a gathering spot for motivated people with similar interests."
- "Provided insight into diverse perspectives which should help break down silo walls."

Collaboration and Networking: Networking and collaboration were seen as key outcomes of the summit:

- "It brought together professionals from various disciplines. This interdisciplinary collaboration will help encourage the integration of different perspectives and expertise."
- "By fostering disciplines from various fields of science."

Defining the Field: The summit prompted discussions about defining Earth Data Science and its research priorities:

- "I think the Innovation Summit made it clear that the definition needs to be communicated better."
- "Understanding data gaps, data needs, data processing pipelines and their gaps, coding and computing needs, supporting and supplementing those needs."

Interdisciplinary Focus: The summit encouraged an interdisciplinary approach:

- "For [myself] and others that attended, it put EDS into a more interdisciplinary mental category than it was previously."
- "Cross-domain facilitated synthesis with necessary computer resources and expertise at hand."

Empowering Early Career Researchers: The summit was seen as empowering students and early-career researchers:

- "Brought new people in (me!) who were interested and intimidated before."
- "Helped interdisciplinary collaboration, steps forward toward building an earth data science adjacent community."

Participants' Take-Aways from the Summit

The responses from Summit participants provide valuable insights into the key takeaways they gained from the ESILL Innovation Summit. Below are common themes identified among their responses:

- **Contacts and Networking:** Many participants mentioned that they made new contacts and connections in the field of EDS. Networking and building relationships with like-minded individuals and potential collaborators were a significant benefit of the summit.
- **Ideas and Inspiration:** Several participants highlighted that they gained new ideas and perspectives during the summit. These ideas ranged from incorporating inclusivity and diversity into EDS to exploring innovative approaches and collaborations.
- **Resources and Skills:** Participants mentioned gaining access to various resources and skills. These included knowledge about available datasets, tools like CyVerse and Jetstream, and insights into cloud computing resources. Some also mentioned improving their communication and collaboration skills.
- **Inclusivity and Indigenous Data Sovereignty:** There was a notable emphasis on the importance of inclusivity and indigenous data sovereignty in EDS. Participants expressed a deeper understanding of these issues and a commitment to addressing them in their work.
- **Collaboration and Interdisciplinary Work:** Many participants expressed a desire for true interdisciplinary collaboration and teamwork. They saw the potential for combining expertise from different fields to address complex environmental challenges.
- **Data Science Education:** Some participants mentioned learning about resources and opportunities for data science education and upskilling. This reflects a recognition of the importance of continuous learning in the field.
- **Community and Advocacy:** Several participants mentioned a sense of community and the importance of advocacy in EDS. They discussed the need for environmental data scientists to work together and advocate for responsible and inclusive practices.
- **Reflection and Ethical Considerations:** Some participants highlighted the need for reflection and ethical considerations in EDS. They discussed the importance of considering the socio-cultural aspects of scientific questions and integrating ethics into the field.
- **Cyberinfrastructure:** The summit provided participants with insights into available cyberinfrastructure resources, such as access to computing resources and data platforms like CyVerse and Google BigQuery.
- **Open Data and Inclusivity:** There was a strong emphasis on open data and making data more available and accessible. Participants recognized the value of inclusivity and diversity in data science.

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Appendix A: 2023 ESIL Innovation Summit Agenda

Face-to-Face Participant Agenda

Summit "Day-Zero" Activities

Plan to arrive early for the summit and join us for a program of optional Pre-Summit Activities

12:30 PM MDT	Early Registration Let us know you are here!	SEEC Atrium
01:00 PM MDT	(Concurrent) Leadership in Environmental Data Science kick-off workshop - Susan Sullivan, CIRES Director of Diversity and Inclusion & Bec Batchelor, CIRES Education & Outreach This workshop will engage you in thinking about yourself as a leader, in preparation for the Summit ahead. In addition to recognizing the types of leadership that will be required to advance the field, we will tackle the thorny questions of feeling like an imposter, especially in a diverse disciplinary environment, recognize the leadership skills you already bring to the table, and empower you to lean into leadership throughout the meeting.	SEEC Auditorium
01:00 PM MDT	(Concurrent) Technical Help Desk - Ty Tuff, ESIL Data Scientist, Tyson Swetnam, CyVerse Liaison We're available to answer any questions you may have from the Virtual Technical Training Sessions.	SEEC Viz Studio
02:00 PM MDT	BREAK	
02:15 PM MDT	Leading with cultural intelligence to advance environmental data science - James Rattling Leaf Sr., ESIL Tribal Liaison Cultural Intelligence is becoming a 'must have' to be able to relate and work effectively with people from a diversity of backgrounds. Join this talk to learn about cultural intelligence, why it is important and how you can improve your CQ.	SEEC Auditorium
03:15 PM MDT	BREAK	
03:30 PM MDT	Expanding the Scope of Team Science: Three Lenses for Thinking about Collaboration in Synthesis - John N. Parker, University of Oslo The Science of Team Science has emerged as an influential field focused on understanding the social conditions that facilitate scientific work. The success of the field is evident, but it remains divided from other ways of conceptualizing and researching scientific groups. This talk will address the possibility of a more holistic approach to investigating scientific teams combining ideas from the Science of Team Science, the Sociology of Science/STS, and Group Dynamics research. It will also relate key findings from past research on synthesis working groups.	SEEC Auditorium
04:00 PM MDT	Informal Social Mixer	SEEC Café

Day One (F2F)

08:30 AM MDT	Registration Make sure we know you are here & find your way around	SEEC Atrium
09:00 AM MDT	Welcome, Call to Action, Goals and Ceremonial Welcome Jennifer Balch, Director, ESIL Philimon D. Two Eagle, Executive Director of the Sicangu Lakota Treaty Council Massimo Ruzzene, V.C. Research, University of Colorado Chelsea Nagy, Associate Director, ESIL	Summit Plenary
09:45 AM MDT	Hopes and Fears What do you want to get out of the Summit?	Summit Plenary
10:25 AM MDT	Provocation Stimulus from Paula Mabee (NEON) - Jim Sanovia (CU/AIHEC)	Summit Plenary
10:45 AM MDT	BREAK Refresh yourselves	SEEC Atrium
11:15 AM MDT	Summit Overview A detailed briefing on what we are going to do and how we will work.	Summit Plenary
11:55 AM MDT	Breakout One Explore the Challenges and Opportunities with colleagues	Summit Plenary or Zoom Breakouts
12:30 PM MDT	LUNCH Grab something to eat and find someone interesting to talk to	SEEC Atrium (and outside if the weather is fine)
01:30 PM MDT	Provocation 2 Explore the Cyverse Universe	Summit Plenary
02:00 PM MDT	Breakout 2 Explore different Challenges and Opportunities with new colleagues	Summit Plenary or Zoom Breakouts
03:00 PM MDT	BREAK Refresh yourselves	SEEC Atrium
03:30 PM MDT	Converge on your most interesting Challenge Choose a Challenge or Opportunity that really interests or excites you	Summit Plenary
04:30 PM MDT	Share Back Share your most interesting Challenges and Opportunities	Summit Plenary
05:00 PM MDT	Next steps and CLOSE Get outside, relax and take it easy	Beautiful Boulder

Day Two (F2F)

08:30 AM MDT	Early Coffee & Tea Time to reconvene and set up for the day :-)	SEEC Atrium
09:00 AM MDT	Welcome Back What happened yesterday and what will happen today	Summit Plenary
09:20 AM MDT	Provocation 3 Stimulus from Sara Beery (MIT) and Sparkle Malone (Yale)	Summit Plenary 📅
09:40 AM MDT	Choose your research question What project do you wish to work on?	Summit Plenary & KIS Storm
10:00 AM MDT	Find your team Identify who you want to work with	Summit Plenary & KIS Storm
10:30 AM MDT	BREAK Refresh yourselves	SEEC Atrium or get outside if you can
11:00 AM MDT	Develop your approach Collaborate to set up your project	Breakout Rooms
12:30 PM MDT	LUNCH Grab something to eat and find someone interesting to talk to (or take a deserved break)	SEEC Atrium (and outside if the weather is fine)
01:30 PM MDT	Soap Boxes Share things that colleagues might find interesting	Summit Plenary
02:00 PM MDT	Present your Approach And get peer feedback to strengthen your thoughts	Summit Plenary & KIS Storm
03:00 PM MDT	BREAK Refresh yourselves	SEEC Atrium
03:30 PM MDT	Refine & Strengthen your approach Assimilate your feedback and strengthen your approach - change teams if you wish	Breakout Rooms
04:30 PM MDT	CLOSE Get outside, relax and take it easy	Beautiful Boulder or wherever you call home
04:30 PM MDT	Funding Clinics After we close Tyson Swetnam will host an informal "clinic" to answer your questions on how to apply for support to use CyVerse.	Summit Plenary

Day Three (F2F)

08:30 AM MDT	Early Coffee & Tea Time to reconvene and set up for the day :-)	SEEC Atrium
09:00 AM MDT	Welcome Back and PHOTO Look your best for the Paparazzi	Summit Plenary
09:30 AM MDT	Provocation 4 Stimulus from Kali Dale - Postdoc and Lab Director for the Native BioData Consortium and John Parker - ESIL Science of Team Science Lead, University of Oslo	Summit Plenary
10:00 AM MDT	Community needs and solutions What are the things we need as a community to take our shared endeavour forward?	Breakout Rooms
11:00 AM MDT	Share Back Share your most interesting community needs	Summit Plenary
11:15 AM MDT	CLOSE Say warm farewells and close that Zoom window	Summit Plenary

Virtual Participant Agenda

Day One (Virtual)

Click on the large green "Join Zoom" button to join us virtually.

11:00 AM MDT	Ceremonial Welcome, Call to Action and Goals Philimon D. Two Eagle, Executive Director of the Sicangu Lakota Treaty Council Jennifer Balch, Director, ESIL Chelsea Nagy, Associate Director, ESIL	Summit Plenary
11:15 AM MDT	Summit Overview A detailed briefing on what we are going to do and how we will work.	Summit Plenary
11:35 AM MDT	Provocation 1 (recording) Stimulus from Paula Mabee (NEON) - Jim Sanovia (CU/AIHEC)	Summit Plenary 📺
11:55 AM MDT	Breakout One Explore the Challenges and Opportunities with colleagues	Summit Plenary or Zoom Breakouts
12:35 PM MDT	LUNCH Grab something to eat	Get outside if you can :-)
01:30 PM MDT	Provocation 2 Explore the Cyverse Universe	Summit Plenary 📺
02:00 PM MDT	Breakout 2 Explore different Challenges and Opportunities with new colleagues	Summit Plenary or Zoom Breakouts
02:40 PM MDT	BREAK Refresh yourselves	Get outside if you can :-)
03:10 PM MDT	Converge on your most interesting Challenge Choose a Challenge or Opportunity that really interests or excites you	Summit Plenary or Zoom Breakouts
04:00 PM MDT	Share Back Share your most interesting Challenges and Opportunities	Summit Plenary
04:30 PM MDT	Next steps and CLOSE Get away from those screens, relax and take it easy	Wherever you call home

Day Two (Virtual)

09:00 AM MDT	Welcome Back What happened yesterday and what will happen today	Summit Plenary
09:20 AM MDT	Provocation 3 Stimulus from Sara Beery (MIT) and Sparkle Malone (Yale)	Summit Plenary
09:40 AM MDT	Choose your research question What project do you wish to work on?	Summit Plenary & KISStorm
10:00 AM MDT	Find your team Identify who you want to work with	Summit Plenary & KISStorm
10:30 AM MDT	BREAK Refresh yourselves	SEEC Atrium or get outside if you can
11:00 AM MDT	Develop your approach Collaborate to set up your project	Breakout Rooms
12:30 PM MDT	LUNCH Grab something to eat and find someone interesting to talk to (or take a deserved break)	SEEC Atrium (and outside if the weather is fine)
01:30 PM MDT	Soap Boxes Share things that colleagues might find interesting	Summit Plenary
02:00 PM MDT	Present your Approach And get peer feedback to strengthen your thoughts	Summit Plenary & KISStorm
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03:30 PM MDT	Refine & Strengthen your approach Assimilate your feedback and strengthen your approach - change teams if you wish	Breakout Rooms
04:30 PM MDT	CLOSE Get outside, relax and take it easy	Beautiful Boulder or wherever you call home
04:30 PM MDT	Funding Clinics After we close Tyson Swetnam will host an informal "clinic" to answer your questions on how to apply for support to use CyVerse.	Summit Plenary

Day Three (Virtual)

09:00 AM MDT	Welcome Back and PHOTO Look your best for the Paparazzi	Summit Plenary
09:30 AM MDT	Provocation 4 Stimulus from Kali Dale - Postdoc and Lab Director for the Native BioData Consortium and John Parker - ESIL Science of Team Science Lead, University of Oslo	Summit Plenary
10:00 AM MDT	Community needs and solutions What are the things we need as a community to take our shared endeavour forward?	Breakout Rooms
11:00 AM MDT	Share Back Share your most interesting community needs	Summit Plenary
11:15 AM MDT	CLOSE Say warm farewells and close that Zoom window	Summit Plenary

Appendix B: Evaluation Surveys

2023 ESIIIL Summit Pre-Survey

ESIIIL Innovation Summit participants were selected based on their ability to help build the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community of the future. **Understanding the thoughts and opinions of Innovation Summit participants is therefore crucial.** Please fill out the information below to the best of your ability.

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: *We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.*

Please provide your first and last name

Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS). Select all that apply.

- People working in Environmental, Biological, Social Science field
- People working in Computational and/or Data Science field
- Data provider
- (Data science) Educator
- Application partner
- Industry representative
- Synthesis center member
- Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Analytics professional
- Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations
- Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations
- Student
- Other. Please describe. _____

In which format will you participate in the ESIIIL Innovation Summit?

- In-person
- Virtual

Did you participate in a Pre-Summit Brainstorming Session?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

*Display This Question:
If Did you participate in a Pre-Summit Brainstorming Session? = Yes*

Please provide any feedback on the Pre-Summit Brainstorming Sessions.

What would you like to get out of your participation in the ESIIIL Innovation Summit? Please share **1 - 3 personal goals** you have for the summit.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIIIL Innovation Summit is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the

current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					

[Section on Social Network Analysis removed. These data are summarized in a separate report.]

[Section on EDS community Needs Assessment removed. These data are summarized in a separate report.]

ESIL holds inclusion as a core principle and method for diversifying environmental data science at a time when society needs all perspectives, and science needs to serve all. The questions below invite you to provide demographic information that will help us better understand who currently participates in ESIL activities and events and will inform our approaches to inclusion to better serve ESIL’s mission. You are never required to provide this information. Responses to all questions are voluntary.

What is your primary role in the broad field of EDS? Please select one.

- Director/Program Manager
- Project/Field Manager
- Analyst
- Technician
- Researcher
- Educator (Lecturer/K-12/Informal/Teaching Faculty)
- Student
- Other _____

Which of the following best describes your current career stage?

- Early Career (I am an undergraduate student, graduate student, post-doctoral fellow, or have 0 to 5 years of professional experience.)
- Mid-Career (I have 6 to 15 years of professional experience.)
- Senior (I have more than 15 years of professional experience.)
- Other. Please describe. _____

What best describes the organization in which you work?

- K-12 or Informal Education
- Academic (higher education)
- Government: Federal
- Government: State
- Government: Local
- Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc)
- Non-profit: other
- Private for-profit
- Industry
- Self
- Other: _____

Are you affiliated with an academic institution?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = Yes

With which type of academic institution are you affiliated? Select all that apply.

- Community College/ 2-yr College
- Professional Program
- Tribal College or Tribal-Serving Institution (TCU)
- Historically Black University (HBCU)
- Minority Serving Institution (MSI)
- Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI)
- American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)
- Primarily Undergraduate Serving
- Undergraduate and Graduate Serving
- Research Intensive (R1/R2/etc)
- If none of the options fit, how would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = No

How would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

Which of the following categories best describe your highest level of education?

- Some high school
- High school diploma or equivalent
- Vocational training
- Some college
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AE, AFA, AS, ASN)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BBA, BFA, BS)
- Some graduate work
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MBA, MFA, MS, MSW)
- Applied or professional graduate degree (e.g. MD, DDS, JD)
- Doctoral degree (e.g. EdD, PhD)
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

In what field did you receive your highest degree?

What are(is) the main professional societies(y) to which you belong?

In which disciplinary field(s) of Environmental Data Science do you MAINLY work? Select all that apply.

- Environmental Science
- Computer/Data Science
- Social Science
- Economics
- Geoscience (Geology, Geography)
- Biological science
- Engineering
- Math
- Other. Please specify. _____

We collect demographic information for three reasons: 1) to hold ourselves accountable for meeting our diversity goals, including to provide opportunities for voices that may not have been well represented in Environmental Data Sciences; 2) to ensure that ESIL meets the needs of a national community; 3) to be able to share aggregated, non-identified data in publications and reports; and 4) to conduct basic research on the social dynamics and outcomes of scientific collaborations and teams. You are never required to provide this information. Responses to all questions are voluntary. How do you currently describe your gender identity? Select all that apply.

- Woman
- Man
- Transgender
- Non-binary
- Gender non-conforming
- I identify as: _____
- I prefer not to answer

Do you identify as LGBTQ+?

LGBTQ+ includes (but isn't limited to) Agender, Aromantic, Asexual, Bisexual, Gay, Gender fluid, Gender non-conforming, Genderqueer, Intersex, Lesbian, Non-binary, Pansexual, Queer, Questioning, Trans, and Two spirit.

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

Please select the racial/ethnic group(s) with which you identify. Select all that apply.

- Black, African American, or African
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian or Asian American
- White, Caucasian, European, or European American
- Hispanic or Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
- Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
- Pacific Islander or Native Hawaiian
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

We realize the above options for describing your racial and ethnic identity are not all inclusive. If you would like, you can tell us how you would prefer to describe your racial and ethnic identity.

Do you identify as having a disability or as being neurodiverse?

Disability/neurodiversity status includes (but is not limited to) those who are Deaf or have serious difficulty hearing; Blind or have serious difficulty seeing even when wearing glasses; those who have serious difficulty walking or climbing stairs; those with a serious disability related to a physical condition; those with a serious disability related to a mental or emotional condition, or those with known conditions of neurodiversity.

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

To help us develop ESIL so that the project is as accessible as possible, please describe any accommodations that would be needed for you to participate optimally in virtual and in-person events:

Are you a member of the U.S. Armed Forces?

- Yes, I am currently serving
- Yes, I am a Veteran
- No, I am not a member of the U.S. Armed Forces
- I prefer not to answer

Have either of your parents or guardians completed a Bachelor's degree or higher (Masters, PhD)?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

Where do you live?

I live in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

I am outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

I prefer not to answer

Where is your place of work located?

Place of work is in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

Place of work is outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

I prefer not to answer

ESIIIL Innovation Summit 2023 Reflection Survey

Thank you for joining us for the ESIIIL Innovation Summit. The ESIIIL leadership team would like to learn about your experiences at the summit in order to better understand its impacts on innovation and building a broader and more inclusive Environmental Data Science network. Your feedback will help us to continue to improve future summits as we build the broader ESD community.

Please provide your first and last name.

In which way did you participate in the Innovation Summit?

In-person, local participant

In-person, out-of-town participant

Virtually

What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply.

- Speaker or Presenter
- Breakout group leader
- ESIIIL leadership team
- ESIIIL advisory board member
- Participant
- Technical helper or Mentor
- Strategic partner

In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply.

- Scoping the Future of Environmental Data Science: Brainstorming Sessions
 - Technical Trainings for Collaboration in Environmental Data Science
 - Optional Pre-Summit Activities (May 22nd afternoon)
-

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. = Technical Trainings for Collaboration in Environmental Data Science

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following components of the Pre-Summit Technical Trainings prepared you for the summit?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
KnowInnovation platform (KISStorm)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
CyVerse Discovery Environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cloud-based computing workstations (JetStream2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
R & Python bilingualism	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tools for open and reproducible science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. = Technical Trainings for Collaboration in Environmental Data Science

In what ways could the Technical Training Modules be improved?

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. = Optional Pre-Summit Activities (May 22nd afternoon)

To what extent do you agree or disagree that each of the following optional activities offered on Monday were useful to you?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I did not attend
Leaning into Leadership	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cultural Intelligence	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tribal Engagement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborations in Scientific Teams	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. = Optional Pre-Summit Activities (May 22nd afternoon)

In what ways could the Pre-Summit Activities be improved?

Overall, I was satisfied with the ESIIIL Innovation Summit.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

What were the best parts of the ESIIIL Innovation Summit?

How could the ESIIIL Innovation Summit be improved?

In which ways did the Innovation Summit meet your expectations and in which ways did it not?

How would you rate the investment of your time?

- Extremely well invested
- Well invested
- Unsure
- My time could have been better invested elsewhere.

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following parts of the ESILL Innovator Summit were effective?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Speed Networking (small groups at assigned tables)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provocations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout Group Time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Balance of participation (active/passive learning)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social Activities (e.g., informal social mixer)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community Discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reflections and Daily Wrap up	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The ESILL Innovation Summit followed an Unconference Format. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree that the following characteristics of this format were implemented successfully.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
The breakout group topics were relevant to attendees.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were opportunities for participants to directly influence what was happening each day at the Summit.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There was an emphasis on welcoming the contributions of every participant.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitation of the Summit was inclusive and welcoming of all ideas regardless of background experience (i.e., no idea is too trivial)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The atmosphere of the Summit was relaxed, open, friendly and fun.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The atmosphere of the Summit was welcoming for newcomers and those new to EDS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were adequate opportunities to network with people of shared interests in EDS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participants learned about and/or applied useful skills or tools related to EDS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were opportunities for collaborative, transdisciplinary work and exchange of ideas.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
The goals of sessions were clearly communicated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting was well-facilitated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers and presenters were engaging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were plenty of networking opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social activities (informal mixers) were appropriate	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The KISTorm virtual venue platform was easy to use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interactive communication through Slack was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If In which way did you participate in the Innovation Summit? = Virtually

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about your virtual participation?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Virtual participants were included appropriately in the Summit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Virtual participants had effective ways to engage with the Summit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Virtual facilitation was done well	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The unconference format worked well in the virtual space	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Networking in the virtual space was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If In which way did you participate in the Innovation Summit? = Virtually

Please provide any feedback on the virtual participation experience of the ESIL Innovation Summit.

The statements below focus on how the technical support and cyberinfrastructure was helpful for your success at the Summit. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with each statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I gained a broader understanding of data science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I gained a broader understanding of cyberinfrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about new opportunities for the synthesis of data in my field	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about a new technology or techniques that I can apply in my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about the ESIL **Innovation Summit overall**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Colleagues showed a general respect for one another	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The contributions of all group members were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagreements were handled constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting code of conduct was consistently implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about **your own experiences** during the meeting, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I felt respected by my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others in my group respected my expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt my contributions were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I handled disagreements constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Breakout groups gathered a group of enthusiastic collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout group brainstorming was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups developed initial plans for projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups created an outline for a project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups developed a plan to collaborate beyond the Summit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Plans for the future breakout group collaboration seem feasible	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent are you motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

Please provide any other feedback you have on the breakout groups.

Display This Question:

*If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Breakout group leader
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member*

What impacts do you anticipate the ESIL Innovation Summit will have over the next 6 months?

Display This Question:

*If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Breakout group leader
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member*

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit will lead to innovation?

Display This Question:

*If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Breakout group leader
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member*

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit will shape a decadal research agenda of EDS?

In which ways do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit advanced the field of Earth Data Science?

Please describe up to three new things that you will take away from the ESIL Innovation Summit (e.g., skills, ideas, contacts, other resources, etc.).

Please elaborate on **the top two** most important or exciting new connections or collaborations you have made during the Summit towards innovation in your work. (Please include the names of people and their affiliations and/or organizations where appropriate)

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit has shaped your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Which of the pictures above best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional after having participated in the ESIL Innovation Summit?

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>				
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>				

Please share any other feedback you have about the ESIL Innovator Summit.

We will organize focus groups over the next two months to debrief with Summit participation and offer a \$20 gift card to participants. If you are willing to participate in a 45-60 min focus group to discuss your experience at the ESIL Summit, please provide your email address.
